

Linkage analysis between *Bph1* and RFLP markers on chromosome 12.

Gene pair AB	Segregation mode in F ₃						c ^{2a}	Recombination value (%)	Genetic map distance (cM)
	A_BB	A_Bb	A_bb	aaBB	aaBb	aabb			
<i>Bph1</i> - G148	20	0	41	1	0	24	10.9 (<0.01)	18.4 ± 10.1	19.3 ± 10.3
<i>Bph1</i> - C185	61	0	5	7	0	17	39.1 (<0.001)	11.5 ± 3.6	11.7 ± 3.6
<i>Bph1</i> - XNpb248	20	42	6	0	4	20	54.5 (<0.001)	10.7 ± 3.4	10.9 ± 3.4
<i>Bph1</i> - XNpb304-1	19	42	6	0	5	19	48.6 (<0.001)	11.9 ± 3.6	12.1 ± 3.6
<i>Bph1</i> - XNpb319	18	42	6	0	5	19	48.6 (<0.001)	11.9 ± 3.6	12.2 ± 3.6
<i>Bph1</i> - XNpb304-2	21	40	6	0	5	19	49.1 (<0.001)	12.1 ± 3.6	12.3 ± 3.6
<i>Bph1</i> - XNpb336	20	38	9	1	6	17	33.0 (<0.001)	18.9 ± 4.5	19.9 ± 4.5
<i>Bph1</i> - XNpb316	21	33	14	2	9	13	12.5 (<0.01)	30.3 ± 5.6	35.2 ± 5.6
<i>Bph1</i> - G124-1	18	36	7	2	14	8	6.6 (<0.01)	32.7 ± 5.9	38.1 ± 6.0

^aCalculated based on the ratio of 3:6:3:1:2:1 (df 2).

However, *Bph1* was not linked to the 21 RFLP markers on chromosome 1. We therefore used several RFLP markers located on the other 10 chromosomes to obtain the marker linked to *Bph1*. The results showed that *Bph1* was linked to G148, C185, XNpb248, and XNpb304-1 on chromosome 12 at recombination values of 18.4, 11.5, 10.7, and 11.9%, respectively (see table). Thus, we conclude that *Bph1* is located on chromosome 12. These loci are arranged as G148 - C 185 - *Bph1* - XNpb248 - XNpb304-1 - XNpb319 - XNpb304-2 (see figure).

However, results of earlier studies (Ikeda and Kaneda 1983, Ikeda 1985) were inconsistent with our findings. Mistakes during trisomic analysis for insect and

disease resistance are possible. Weak and scanty trisomic plants that have the resistance gene may appear susceptible under resistance selection pressure. The recombination value of 39.4% between *bph2* and *d2* is also too distant to confirm a linkage relationship. Previous studies did not use marker genes on chromosome 12. Use of several RFLP markers on all chromosomes enabled us to determine the location of *Bph1* on chromosome 12.

Cited references

Idetd O, Yoshimura A, Iwata N. 1994. Integration of convention and RFLP linkage map in rice. V. The locus *ebisu dwarf* (*d2*) [in Japanese]. *Breed. Sci.* 44 (suppl.2): 185.

Arrangement of *Bph1* and RFLP markers on chromosome 12. The genetic distances are given in centimorgan units.

Ikeda R. 1985. Studies on the inheritance of resistance to the rice brown planthopper (*Nilaparvata lugens* Stål) and the breeding of resistant rice cultivars [in Japanese]. *Bull. Natl. Agric. Res. Cent.* 3:1-54.

Ikeda R, Kaneda C. 1983. Trisomic analysis of the gene *Bph1* for resistance to the brown planthopper, *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål., in rice. *Jpn. J. Breed.* 33:40-44. ■

Stress tolerance—salinity

Principal component analysis and variety classification in relation to rice seedling salinity tolerance

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Salinity is one of the major constraints to rice production in Cuba; improved salt-tolerant varieties are essential for achieving economically important gains in yield. We evaluated the salinity tolerance of some varieties important to rice breeding programs in eastern Cuba.

Distilled water (EC 0.02 dS m⁻¹) was used as the laboratory medium and as a control. Salinity stress (EC 12 dS m⁻¹) was

adjusted by adding NaCl. Twenty seeds were kept in each solution in petri dishes, with five replications. Water volume was maintained by adding solution. Root length, seedling height, and fresh and dry seedling matter were measured after 7 d. Salinity tolerance indexes (STI) were calculated using the equation STI (%) = 100 (IS/IC), where IS is the mean of saline solution indicator and CL is the mean of the control solution indicator.

Principal component analysis showed that more than 83% of the total variability between varieties was accumulated in the first two components (see table). The STI (based on seedling height and seedling dry matter) in the first component and the STI (based on root length) in the second component appear to have the highest value of correlation with the principal axis, indicating the usefulness of these indexes in classifying varietal tolerance.

Results of principal component analysis.

Characteristic ^a	Principal components	
	1	2
STI based on Ht	0.746	0.009
STI based on RL	0.290	0.634
STI based on FM	-0.538	0.281
STI based on DM	0.732	0.010
Eigenvectors	2.306	0.934
Contribution to variability (%)	68.80	14.30
Total	variability 68.80	83.60

^aSTI = salinity tolerance indexes. Ht = seedling height, RL = root length, FM = seedling fresh matter, and DM = seedling dry matter.

Based on the first two components, cultivars were placed in four groups (see figure), where the variability in cultivar response to salinity was observed. Group I (Caribe 1, IA Cuba-26,2 196, Ecia 22-8, J-

Group I	Group II	Group III	Group IV
002 - Caribe I	008 - Amistad-82	001 - J-104	011 - MI-48
003 - IA Cuba-26	012 - IR8	014 - 2005	016 - 4034
004 - 2196	013 - 6140		019 - Perla
005 - Ecia 22-8	015 - CP ₃ C ₂		
006 - J-112	017 - 4014		
007 - 2006	018 - 4032		
009 - IR42			
010 - IR5931			

112, 2006, IR42, and IR5931), which gave the highest STI values (seedling height = 79%, root length = 81%, and seedling dry matter = 71%), was the most salt-tolerant group.

Use of this method will improve efficiency and save on expenses in breeding programs for seedling tolerance because the most salt-tolerant cultivars can be determined and used. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

Variability, heritability, correlation, path analysis, and genetic divergence studies in M₂ generation of gamma-irradiated upland rice

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We studied the genotypic and phenotypic coefficients of variation, heritability, genetic advance (GA), coefficients of correlation, path analysis, and genetic divergence in 75 M₂ families raised from

eight upland varieties treated with 10-, 20-, 30-, 40-, and 50-kR gamma rays.

Analysis of variance showed significant differences among genotypes for all characters (Table 1). Considerable range of variation was expressed for percent sterility (43.36), tillers plant⁻¹ (14.91), grain yield plant⁻¹ (14.67), and spikelets panicle⁻¹ (13.51), indicating better scope for selection for genetic improvement. Percent sterility had maximum genotypic coefficient of variation (32.23), followed by grain yield plant⁻¹ (29.75), plant height (26.07), spikelets panicle⁻¹ (19.94), tillers plant⁻¹ (13.85), and days to flowering (12.26) and maturity (9.33).

Estimates of heritability ranged from 91.20% for plant height to 35.60% for sterility. Although plant height (91.20), and days to flowering (88.00) and maturity (87.00) had high heritability, these characters had low genotypic coefficients of variation (GCV) values. This might be due to the variation of environmental components involved in these traits. Expected GA ranged from 6.92% (panicle length) to 54.91% (grain yield plant⁻¹). Grain yield plant⁻¹, plant height, percent sterility, and spikelets panicle⁻¹ showed high GA with high GCV values. These characters should therefore be considered in efforts to obtain high genetic gains.

Grain yield plant⁻¹ was positively correlated with tillers plant⁻¹, but was negatively and significantly correlated with days to 50% flowering (-0.409) and maturity (-0.421), plant height (-0.717), panicle length (-0.302), and percent sterility (-0.771). Negative correlation of characters (tillers plant⁻¹, panicle length, and spikelets panicle⁻¹) might be due to the highest correlation ($r^2 = -0.771$) with sterility.

Percent sterility was positively and significantly correlated with plant height (0.579) and panicle length (0.575). Panicle length was found significantly and positively correlated with days to 50% flowering (0.382) and maturity (0.370) and plant height (0.68). Both plant height and tillers plant⁻¹ were significantly and positively correlated with days to flowering (0.416 and 0.376) and maturity (0.425 and 0.361). Days to 50% flowering had a highly significant and positive (0.999) correlation with days to maturity.

Correlation and path analysis studies revealed that filled grains panicle⁻¹, plant height, and panicle length are important yield-contributing characters that must be considered when adopting selection criteria in an upland rice breeding program.

Genetic divergence studies using D2 analysis showed that the 75 M₂ families had formed 14 genetically diverse groups (Table 2). Selection pressure applied on the M₂ families is likely to provide targeted yield and desired combinations of yield-contributing traits in future generations. ■